

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF IRONY IN LITERATURE

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Abstract. *This thesis explores the aesthetic functions and conceptual essence of irony in global literature. It analyzes various forms of irony- including verbal, situational and dramatic- and examines their role in conveying the author's intent. The study argues that irony is not merely a tool for humour but a sophisticated philosophical instrument used to reveal contradictions within society and human nature.*

Keywords: *Irony, sarcasm, literary imagery, subtext, dramatism, literary style.*

Introduction. In literature, irony is a stylistic device that expresses the contradiction between the outward appearance of reality and its inner essence. In contemporary 2025 literary studies, irony is analyzed as a complex cognitive process that not only enhances comedy but also intensifies tragedy, allowing authors to mask critical perspectives.

Body. Irony performs several vital functions within a literary work;

1.Revealing the Truth; For instance, in Sophocles' *Oedipus Rex*, *dramatic irony* demonstrates how the hero's attempt to escape his fate is precisely what leads him to his downfall.

2.Social critique; In Uzbek literature, authors like Abdulla Qodiriy or Abdulla qahhor use irony to subject ignorance and outdated social norms to bitter ridicule.

3.Psychological Depth; Irony reveals a character's internal complexity through self-reflection, highlighting the intricacies of their inner world.

LITERARY REVIEW.

Irony in Shakespeare's Play Julius Caesar; A classic example of irony is Mark Antony's speech in Shakespeare's Julius Caesar. Although Antony declares, 'I come to bury Caesar, not to praise him', and declares that assassins are 'honorable men' he means just the opposite;. Bryan Garner, Garner's Modern American Usage. Oxford University Press, 2009

Uses and Characteristics of Irony. Irony may be used as a rhetorical device to enforce one's meaning. It may be used..... as a satiric device to attack a point of view or to expose folly, hypocrisy, or vanity. It may be used as a heuristic device to lead one's readers to see that things are not so complex or doubtful as they seem. It is probably that most irony is rhetorical, satirical, or heuristic. ...

ANALYSIS.

As a literary device, irony is often misunderstood. Although many of us learn about irony in our high school English classes through works of theater like Shakespeare's Romeo and Juliet or Sophocles's Oedipus Rex, many people feel unsure of what irony means- or how to use it correctly. But when deployed with skill, irony is a powerful tool that adds depth and substance to a piece of writing. The definition of irony as a literary device is a situation in which there is a contrast between expectation and reality. For example, the difference between what something appears to mean versus its literal meaning. Irony is associated with both tragedy and humor.

Irony, in its broadest sense, is a rhetorical device, literary technique, or event characterized by an incongruity, or contrast, between reality and appearance emphasis in the assertion of a truth.

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The ironic form of smile, used in sarcasm and some forms of litotes can emphasize one's meaning by the deliberate use of language which states the opposite of truth, denies the contrary of the truth or drastically and obviously understates a factual connection.

Irony is often an effective way for an author to express ideas of what she thinks describes the society or person does and how they actually live. A society which claims to value truth and justice, but actually tolerates or encourages lying and injustice is ironic. Irony can be used in any number of ways in fiction. In fact there are different categories that can be found in fiction, depending on the types of story being told. For instance, a man who pursues what he thinks is the perfect woman, eventually learns that she isn't as perfect as he or the readers thought.

Conclusion. In conclusion, irony serves to express reality in a multi-layered and profound manner. It completes the reader to think critically about the text and search for the meaning hidden beneath the surface. Without irony a literary work remains one-dimensional; its presence elevates the artistic value intellectual caliber of the narrative.

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